

Swiss Institute of
Bioinformatics

Selection of SIB Resources for the period 2021-2025

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1. Introduction

SIB's Infrastructure Mission

The SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics fosters excellence in data science to support progress in biological research and health. SIB leads and coordinates the field of bioinformatics in Switzerland. SIB's first mission is to provide the national and international life science research community with a state-of-the-art bioinformatics infrastructure, including resources, expertise and services. It consists amongst others of developing, maintaining and disseminating databases, software and services worldwide, as well as offering key competencies and research support to the national biomedical and life science community.

SIB is bound to the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI through a Service Level Agreement (SLA), which covers the provision of bioinformatics resources to the life science community, as well as post-graduate bioinformatics training and the PhD Training Network.

The Board of Directors (BoD) allocates the funding in the context of this SLA to the "SIB Resources", based on recommendations of the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and subject to the availability of funds.

SIB Resources

SIB Resources are **best-in-class databases and software tools that are deemed of particular importance to the life science community** and **fit within the SIB Resource portfolio and its strategic orientation**. SIB Resources show high levels of usage within their target audience, provide excellent scientific quality and service, and are considered an authority in their field. Within the limit of available funding, SIB is committed to ensuring the **long-term existence** of the SIB Resources in order to provide a stable environment for the development, enhancement and maintenance of these high-quality databases and software tools to support the life science community. In [Section 5.1](#), the SIB Resources for the period 2017-2021 are listed.

SIB's support throughout the life cycle of the SIB Resources

A new database or software tool typically starts with a research project, leading to a proof-of-concept. Through further development, it evolves towards maturity and may become part of the research infrastructure of the scientific community (figure 1). **Within the context of the SERI SLA, SIB can only support infrastructure**. The funding it receives from SERI cannot be used for research activities or short-term projects.

Figure 1: The life cycle of a bioinformatics resource.

SIB's support can go to promising emerging resources, as well as to fully mature ones. As described below, a set of indicators provide quality standards for the resources, guide and inform the managers of emerging services in the life cycle management of their resource and its development into a mature infrastructure, and inform their monitoring, for example by the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB).

To promote new developments at the highest level of scientific excellence, SIB is committed to identify and support **additions to its resource portfolio among the emerging or already well-established resources** developed by SIB groups, and which have a (potentially) high impact on the life science community. These resources must have passed the **proof-of-concept** stage and reached a sufficient level of development and usage to be considered as infrastructure. They should demonstrate their uniqueness, a strong demand from the target community and alignment with Open Data practices, in addition to high scientific standards.

SIB's support to Resources takes two forms:

- a) **A portfolio of services** that support professional infrastructure provision, including User Experience (UX) studies and design, hosting, best practices & knowledge sharing, security audit, user training, as well as licensing and legal advice.

and/or

- b) **The provision of funds** that allow hiring skilled personnel to develop and maintain the resource. The mission of SIB is to maintain a portfolio of SIB Resources over the long-term and fund the SIB Resources within this portfolio as long as they have a high impact in the life science community. It is the role of the SAB to evaluate this impact and give recommendations regarding the level of funding. The available funding that can be allocated to new SIB Resources is not known yet and depends on

the future funding levels. It is however, per definition, limited. In principle, SIB commits to supporting resources along the entire funding period (2021-2025). However, the SIB Resources are evaluated by the SAB at mid-term, typically two years after the initial assignment. This mid-term review includes an evaluation of the progress made since the beginning of the period. Based on the outcome, the BoD can decide to adjust the funding level or stop funding the resource.

SIB Resources' commitments

Being a SIB Resource implies a close collaboration between the Resource and SIB's internal teams. A SIB Resource benefits from the portfolio of services listed previously, and is integrated in the network of SIB Resources within which it collaborates in order to improve the overall quality and impact of the SIB Resources portfolio. Collaborations, synergies, and interoperability across the Resources are expected and the knowledge and expertise within SIB are shared between the Resource Managers.

Receiving support as SIB Resource is also subject to specific conditions:

1. The Resource Manager(s) and their collaborators, SIB Employees or not, should fulfil their obligations according to the "SIB Employee Regulations" and the "SIB Member Regulations" respectively. A particular attention should be given to the obligation for all SIB Members to indicate their SIB affiliation on their publications, including presentations and press releases, and include the SIB logo when appropriate. The SIB identity must be made clearly visible in all types of communication, distribution or dissemination of the Resource. Web Resources must apply the SIB guidelines for websites, unless consortium agreements prohibit this.
2. A SIB Resource and its staff are asked to collaborate with the various SIB Management departments when necessary.
3. The Group Leader who is responsible for the Resource must participate in all CGL meetings (typically once or twice per year) and show strong SIB involvement (e.g. participation in consultations, training).
4. Every Resource is strongly encouraged to set up its own Advisory Committee with scientists and/or users, to complement the input of the SIB SAB which advises SIB on its entire Resource portfolio.
5. The Resource Manager has to seek additional funding for the concerned Resource.

Timelines

The Swiss Parliament votes on funding for research, education and innovation for the ERI period 2021-2024 at the end of 2020. In December 2020 or beginning 2021, SIB will be informed of the funding levels for the

Institute for 2021-2024. The SAB will meet in April 2021, following the procedure, criteria and timeline described below. In Summer 2021, based on the report of the SAB and taking into account the available funding, the SIB BoD will decide on the funding levels for the SIB Resources for the period 2022-2025 (for existing SIB Resources) and September 2021-2025 for new SIB Resources.

2. Selection criteria

SIB Resources are defined as **best-in-class databases and software tools that are deemed of particular importance to the life science community and fit within the SIB Resource portfolio and its strategic orientation**. SIB Resources show high levels of usage within their target audience, excellent scientific quality and service, and are considered an authority in their field.

The funding will exclusively be used to cover the development and maintenance of the SIB Resource.

SIB's high-quality infrastructure, i.e. databases and software tools, as well as the associated services, are driven by excellence in research. SIB Resources can thus be linked to research work or have a research component. In agreement with its SLA with SERI, this associated research can only be funded by other means such as SNSF or the European Commission, and not by SERI art. 15 funds, even if it is intended to build a bioinformatics resource in the future.

The workplan for a SIB Resource must meet the following criteria:

1. Demonstrate high quality of data and metadata, respond to a clear scientific need, and be unique. This implies benchmarking against other resources, and being an authority in its field compared to the major competitors (**Criterion I, Scientific focus and quality of science**).
2. Know the community to whom it is addressed, its size and the usage: web statistics, user reach, and community size. Candidate resources with a valid track record of usage, responding to a clear need within the scientific community are more likely to be included as SIB Resources. However, emerging resources are encouraged to submit as well. The scientific context in which the resource operates should be taken into account. A resource that serves a small scientific community may not have as many users as a resource serving a broader interest, and yet it may reach 90% of the community it supports (coverage) and be crucial for the scientific work of that community (**Criterion II, Community**).
3. Demonstrate a high level of service and reliability with the integration of features such as persistent and unique identifiers, community-recognized standards, user support and training, as well as the integration of user feedback (**Criterion III, Quality of the service**).

4. Have a sound legal framework supporting Open Science and seek complementary funds from other sources in order to ensure sustainable long-term funding (**Criterion IV, Legal and funding infrastructure and governance**).
5. Have a significant impact on the life science community and be impact-driven (**Criterion V, Impact and translational stories**).

As described in the “SIB Group Leaders and General Membership” document, Group Leaders who manage a SIB Resource are expected to participate in the meetings of the Council of Group Leaders (CGL, typically 1-2 times per year) and show strong involvement in SIB. Therefore, provided the above mentioned criteria are met, the level of involvement in SIB of a Group Leader submitting a workplan for a resource will also be taken into consideration in the evaluation (**Criterion VI, SIB**).

3. Indicators

Indicators are used to assess the alignment of the (candidate and existing) SIB Resources with the above criteria. Providing precise information and figures for these indicators allows the panel of external reviewers and the SAB to make an objective recommendation.

For indicators relating to web access, information will be obtained automatically from insights.expasy.org based on Google Analytics. For candidate SIB Resources, figures must be provided, preferably as extracted from Google Analytics. If Google Analytics is not available for the candidate SIB Resource, all relevant information with respect to the usage figures for the resource must be provided. Depending on the type of resource, different indicators will be relevant, and information should only be provided when applicable. The evaluations will take into account the diversity of the resources, thus, indicators will be assessed differently depending on the type of resource. For example, it is fully acceptable to have low page views for a resource that is mainly accessed via FTP.

4. Procedure

The Board of Directors (BoD) is responsible for selecting the SIB Resources, as well as for the allocation of federal funds to said resources¹. Decisions are based on the recommendations of the SAB that, for candidate SIB Resources, takes input from evaluations by external reviewers. Members of the BoD do not take part in decisions for which they have a conflict of interest.

¹ Article 7.2 of the SIB Statutes

4.1. How to submit a workplan – Candidates for new SIB Resources

If you intend to submit a workplan for a new SIB Resource, i.e. for a resource that is not listed in Annex 5.1, you need to inform us by sending an email to resources@sib.swiss by 20 August 2020, with **acknowledgement of receipt**. This will enable us to plan the scale of the process. This *intention to submit* needs to contain the following information:

- a. Name of the resource;
- b. Name of the person who will submit the workplan;
- c. Domain to which the resource belongs (Proteomics, Evolutionary Biology, Genomics, ...);
- d. The names and contact details of 4 external reviewers who may be available for reviewing the workplan;
- e. An estimation of the funds that will be needed from SIB (in CHF).

A workplan will not be accepted without this *intention to submit* or if the *intention to submit* has been sent after the indicated date.

Workplans for candidate SIB Resources should be submitted by **4 October 2020** through the online form accessible at: <https://www.sib.swiss/sib-resource-workplans-2021/> (candidate SIB Resources will receive a communication when the link will be active, about one month before the deadline). A sample form is available at [Section 5.2](#) for consultation; only the online form can be used for submission.

The workplans for candidate SIB Resources will be sent to a panel of external reviewers who will rate the individual workplans based on the criteria I to V described in [Section 2](#).

For each of the criteria, the reviewers will assign a score according to a 9-point scale:

- Exceptional (9)
- Outstanding (8)
- Excellent (7)
- Very good (6)
- Good (5)
- Satisfactory (4)
- Fair (3)
- Marginal (2)
- Poor (1)

- The entire scale (1-9) should always be considered,
- The scores of 1 or 9 are expected to be used less frequently than the other scores,
- 5 is considered an average score of a good, medium-impact resource.
- Each score must be justified and commented by the reviewers.

In consultation with the SAB, the workplans with the best evaluations will be invited to present at the SAB meeting on 27-29 April 2021. The selected candidate SIB Resources will be informed **by 11 January 2021** and will be asked to provide additional information in preparation for the meeting, in particular concerning funding levels and staff effort. The deadline for this additional information is fixed at 31 January 2021.

4.2. How to submit a workplan – Current SIB Resources

Workplans for the current SIB Resources (as per table in [Section 5.1](#)) are to be submitted by **31 January 2021** through the online form accessible at: <https://www.sib.swiss/sib-resource-workplans-2021/> (SIB Resources will receive a communication when the link will be active, one month before the deadline). A sample form is available in [Section 5.3](#) for consultation; only the online forms can be used for submission.

The Group Leader(s) in charge will present the workplan during the SAB meeting on 27-29 April 2021.

In case you would no longer wish to benefit from the SIB Resource status and associated support for 2022-2025, please send an email to resources@sib.swiss by **20 August 2020**. The modalities for the continuation of the resource will then have to be discussed with SIB Management.

The SAB reserves the right to request external input for current SIB Resources. The SAB will communicate to SIB Management for which existing SIB resources an external review or input regarding specific questions is needed. In this case, the Group Leader(s) of the respective SIB Resources will be informed in due time.

4.3. The SAB evaluation

At the SAB meeting on 27-29 April 2021, the SAB will evaluate both the existing and the selected candidate SIB Resources. Following the presentations, the SAB will score the workplans and make a recommendation regarding their funding level. Based on the SAB recommendations, the BoD will decide on the portfolio of SIB Resources that will be allocated SERI funding for the period 2021-2025.

Candidate SIB Resources that are evaluated positively by the SAB, but that are not selected by the BoD to be funded due to the limited funding available, can nonetheless, upon agreement with the Resource's provider, be included in the SIB Resource portfolio (cf. [Section 2](#)) to benefit from the associated visibility and SIB services (cf. previous, User Experience studies and design, hosting, best practices & knowledge sharing, security audit, training, licensing and legal advice, as well as mentoring).

4.4 Timeline for the selection process of SIB Resources

3 July 2020	Information sent to Group Leaders
9 July 2020	SIB webinar for Group Leaders: Process for the selection of the SIB Resources
20 August 2020	Notice of intention to submit candidate new SIB Resources
4 Oct 2020	Deadline for submission of full workplan for candidate SIB Resources
Oct-Nov 2020	External review of the workplans for the candidate SIB Resources
Dec 2020	SAB selection of the candidate SIB Resources to be reviewed at the SAB meeting in April 2021
11 Jan 2021	Candidate SIB Resources selected for SAB review are informed
31 Jan 2021	Deadline for submission of the full workplans for current SIB Resources and supplementary information for selected candidate SIB Resources
Feb-Apr 2021	Review of the workplans of selected candidate SIB Resources and current SIB Resources by the SAB
27-29 Apr 2021	SAB meeting: presentations by Group Leaders of the selected candidate SIB Resources and current SIB Resources
Summer 2021	Decision by BoD for 2021-2025
Sep 2021	Funding period of new SIB Resources starts
Jan 2022	Funding period for current SIB Resources starts
Spring 2023	SAB midterm review of SIB Resources

5. Annexes

5.1. List of SIB Resources for the period 2017-2021

Name of the SIB Resource	Current Group Leader in charge
Bgee	Marc Robinson-Rechavi & Frédéric Bastian
EPD	Philipp Bucher
neXtProt	Amos Bairoch & Lydie Lane
STRING	Christian von Mering
SwissDrugDesign	Olivier Michielin & Vincent Zoete
SWISS-MODEL	Torsten Schwede
SwissOrthology (OMA + OrthoDB)	Christophe Dessimoz, Evgeny Zdobnov & Evgenia Kriventseva
SwissRegulon	Erik van Nimwegen
UniProtKB/SwissProt and associated Resources; SwissLipids	Alan Bridge
V-pipe	Niko Beerenwinkel

5.2. Case document for candidate SIB Resources

Please note that only the online form is valid for submission.

Administrative Information

Resource name	
Estimation of funds needed in CHF for the full period (4 years)	
Main person in charge: Surname, first name	
Co-submitter(s): Surname(s), first name(s)	

Whenever quantitative figures are needed (e.g. number of users, accesses, page views), please join the relative extract from Google Analytics.

For certain questions, we distinguished between Databases and Software tools. However, these definitions are not mutually exclusive: for instance, a Database may have associated Software tools. In such a case, respond to each question with respect to the part of the resource that corresponds to the right category.

I <i>Scientific focus and quality of science</i>	
a <i>Definition</i>	The Resource is a <input type="checkbox"/> Database <input type="checkbox"/> Software tool <input type="checkbox"/> Database & Software tool
b <i>Scope statement</i>	Describe the scope and scientific coverage of the Resource (for example, all species or a subset of species, families, outputs from a particular experimental method), as well as the scientific need to which it responds.
c <i>Uniqueness of the resource</i>	Indicate who are the major competitors of the Resource and how the Resource compares to them including benchmarking efforts.
d <i>Potential synergies and collaborations with other SIB Resources</i>	Describe the potential synergies and collaborations with other SIB Resources that could increase the impact of the (respective) Resource(s).

II Community											
a	<p><i>User community</i> Whom is the Resource addressed to? Describe the current user community and the size of the potential user community. Are there other user communities that are currently not yet reached? Include quantitative measurements, if possible.</p>										
b	<p><i>Overall usage - web access</i> Web access as measured by Google Analytics. Please join the following extract from Google Analytics (period: from 2018 to present, or from more recently if not yet available in 2018; view by month):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Audience > overview - Acquisition > overview - Behaviour > overview 										
	<p><i>Overall usage - additional access methods</i> Please give figures to quantify any additional access methods: visits, unique visitors, hits, and downloads (includes FTP downloads and programmatic access)</p>										
c	<p><i>Overall usage (software tools / service platforms)</i> If available, provide statistics about the number of jobs submitted and/or the number of downloads of the software tool and/or any other measurements that assess the usage of the Resource.</p> <p><i>Example:</i></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Type of measurement</th> <th>Value at 31/12/2017</th> <th>Value at 31/12/2018</th> <th>Value at 31/12/2019</th> <th>Value at 31/07/2020</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Jobs submitted</td> <td>100</td> <td>200</td> <td>400</td> <td>500</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Type of measurement	Value at 31/12/2017	Value at 31/12/2018	Value at 31/12/2019	Value at 31/07/2020	Jobs submitted	100	200	400	500
Type of measurement	Value at 31/12/2017	Value at 31/12/2018	Value at 31/12/2019	Value at 31/07/2020							
Jobs submitted	100	200	400	500							
d	<p><i>Usage in research as measured through citation in the literature</i> Go to https://europepmc.org/ and run a query using the relevant keywords, which best identify the Resource. Copy and paste the resulting URL, together with the number of citations (<i>example: https://europepmc.org/search?query=resourceAAB%20%2B%20organism: 35 citations</i>). If necessary, indicate more than one URL, but do not exceed 3.</p> <p>If any extra explanation is needed, you can also add it to the text field. Moreover, if other citation counting tools are more representative of the usage of the Resource, please feel free to report the additional statistics.</p>										
e	<p><i>Dependency of other resources</i> Indicate which resources depend on the Resource .</p> <p><i>Examples:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The UniLectin platform depends on SWISS-MODEL to display molecular interactions between small molecules and protein structures.</i> • <i>PeptideAtlas uses information about single amino acid variants and post-translational modifications in neXtProt to enable processing and display of data.</i> 										
III Quality of Service											
a	<p><i>Unique ID</i> Indicate if the Resource provides persistent and unique identifiers and if yes, describe it.</p>										
b	<p><i>Data entries/record</i> <u>Cumulative</u> total number of entries or records to indicate the growth of the Resource. Please provide a description and explanation on what an “entry” is.</p> <p><i>Example:</i></p>										

s (data resources)	Entry	Description	Value at 31/12/2017	Value at 31/12/2018	Value at 31/12/2019	Value at 31/07/2020
	<i>Species</i>	Number of Species in the Resource	100	200	300	400
	<i>Genes</i>	Number of genes annotated in the Resource	1000	2000	3000	4000
	<i>Variants</i>	Number of sequence variations present in the Resource	200	250	400	410
c	<i>Use of community-recognized standards for (meta)data</i>	Which community-recognized standards are used for metadata and data (e.g. MIAME, JATS, INSDC features, ontologies)? Provide a link to documentation.				
d	<i>Data availability & access (data resources)</i>	Data sharing services: list services through which data is shared (e.g. website, APIs, FTP, TripleStore) Data sharing formats: list formats for available data (e.g. plain text, FASTA, XML, RDF, Dublin Core, tsv, JSON)				
e	<i>Customer service</i>	<u>Helpdesk</u> : does the Resource run a helpdesk? <u>User feedback</u> : how does the Resource seek and incorporate user input into service design decisions? <u>User training</u> : which training is offered by the Resource? (face2face training, eLearning, etc.)				
IV	<i>Legal and funding infrastructure</i>	<i>Indicators IV e, f, g (in red text) will not be asked for the first submission. GLs will be asked to complete this information only if the first SAB selection has been passed (Jan 2021)</i>				
a	<i>Scientific advisory board</i>	Does the Resource have an external independent Advisory Committee with scientists and/or users (other than the SIB SAB)?				
b	<i>Legal framework supporting Open Science?</i>	Does the Resource have terms of use or a licence that enables the reuse and remixing of data? (see Open Definition for a list of open licenses) If yes, please include a link to terms of use or state license designation (e.g. CC0, CC-BY, CC-BY-SA). Is the access to, and/or usage of, the Resource restricted in any way to the user or certain categories of users? If yes, please explain why. If the current legal framework does not support Open Science, do you plan to adopt an open licence?				
c	<i>Licensing code: is it published on open access?</i>	Is the source code of the Resource published in open access (e.g. in GitHub)? If yes, please indicate under which licence and the relevant URLs.				

d	<i>Sustainable support and funding</i>	Describe what has been, and what will be, undertaken to seek additional funds from other sources.																				
e	<i>Staff effort (how many FTEs?) and funding</i>	<p>Overview of all the available funding for the Resource during the period 2017–2021, as well as FTEs devoted to the Resource, including the PI working time. Please specify the type of funding in the first column e.g. SNFS, university, European Commission, or any other source.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Type of funding</th> <th>Period of funding</th> <th>Amount (CHF)</th> <th>FTEs</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>UniBas</td> <td>Jan 2018 - Dec 2019</td> <td>XXX</td> <td>YYY</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UniBas</td> <td>Jan 2018 - Dec 2018</td> <td>ZZZ</td> <td>JJJ</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SNSF</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>...</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Type of funding	Period of funding	Amount (CHF)	FTEs	UniBas	Jan 2018 - Dec 2019	XXX	YYY	UniBas	Jan 2018 - Dec 2018	ZZZ	JJJ	SNSF				...			
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SNSF																						
...																						
f	<i>What would you do with SIB funding?</i>	How do you plan to use the SIB funding? Please detail (in person-months) for what kind of work SIB funding will be used (for example: XX person-months for biocuration, YY person-months for code development, ZZ person-months for dataset selection):																				
V Impact and visibility																						
a	<i>Counterfactual</i>	Description of how science would be affected if the Resource had not existed or was to disappear and not be replaced.																				
b	<i>Accelerating science</i>	Description of how much the Resource accelerates science: present one or more selected examples of how the Resource has been used by its user community, showcasing the importance of the Resource for advancing science. These “translational stories” help SIB to show its impact to audiences such as policy makers and funders and help the SAB to assess the Resource.																				
c	<i>Visibility</i>	What actions has the Resource taken to increase its visibility within its potential user community?																				
VI SIB																						
a	<i>Benefits</i>	How does your Resource contribute to SIB in terms of scientific credibility, visibility or any other aspect?																				
b	<i>Participation</i>	Describe your contributions to SIB in the last 2 years, and how you see your involvement in the coming years																				
c	<i>SIB Portfolio of Resources</i>	How does the Resource align with the current portfolio of SIB Resources?																				

5.3. Case document for current SIB Resources

Please note that only the online form is valid for submission:.

Administrative Information

Resource name	
Estimation of funds needed in CHF for the full period (4 years)	
Main person in charge: Surname, first name Co-submitter(s): Surname(s), first name(s)	

Whenever quantitative figures (e.g. number of users, accesses, page views) can be obtained from insights.expaty.org through Google Analytics, this is indicated and you do not need to provide any data.

In some cases, from previous submissions we already have some of the information asked. In such cases, indicated with a [blue text](#), fields of the online form are pre-filled with known data. Please check if the information is correct and update if necessary.

For certain questions, we distinguished between Databases and Software tools. However, these definitions are not mutually exclusive: for instance, a Database may have associated Software tools. In such a case, respond to each question with respect to the part of the resource that corresponds to the right category.

Achievements and workplan

a	<i>Summary of work, results & impact [Jan 2019 - Dec 2020]</i>	Provide an overview of the most recent work, results and impact of the Resource for the period Jan 2019 - Dec 2020.
b	<i>Fulfilment of the objectives [Jan 2019 - Dec 2020]</i>	Please describe to what extent the objectives and implementation plan presented in your SAB mid-term review submission form submitted in 2019 were realized. If they were not (or not completely) attained, explain why.

c	<i>Review SAB comments and respond</i>	In May 2019, the Resource was reviewed by the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB). You can find an extract of the report below. Please respond to the review and describe how the required actions have been implemented [<i>followed by extract from the SAB report 2019 – general comments</i>].										
d	<i>Objectives and implementation plan for 2022-2025</i>	Describe the objectives and implementation plan for the next funding period.										
e	<i>Potential synergies and collaborations with other SIB Resources</i>	Describe the potential synergies and collaborations with other SIB Resources that could increase the impact of the (respective) Resource(s).										
I Scientific focus and quality of science												
a	<i>Definition:</i>	The resource is a <input type="checkbox"/> Database <input type="checkbox"/> Software tool <input type="checkbox"/> Database & Software tool										
b	<i>Scope statement: scientific coverage and comprehensiveness</i>	Describe the scientific coverage and comprehensiveness of the Resource (for example, all species or a subset of species, families, outputs from a particular experimental method), as well as the scientific need to which it responds.										
c	<i>Uniqueness of the resource</i>	Indicate who are the major competitors of the Resource and how the Resource compares to them including benchmarking efforts.										
II Community												
a	<i>User Community</i>	Whom is the Resource addressed to? In order to assess the impact of the Resource, describe your current user community and compare it to the potential global audience. Include quantitative measurements, if possible.										
b	<i>Overall usage - web access</i>	Information will be obtained automatically from insights.expasy.org based on Google Analytics.										
	<i>Overall usage - additional access methods</i>	Please give figures to quantify any additional access methods: visits, unique visitors, hits, and downloads (includes FTP downloads and programmatic access).										
c	<i>Usage of the resource (software tools / service platforms)</i>	If available, provide statistics about the number of jobs submitted and/or the number of downloads of the software tool and/or any other measurements that assess the usage of the Resource. <i>Example:</i>										
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d	<i>Usage in research as measured through citation in the literature</i>	Go to https://europepmc.org/ and run a query using the relevant keywords, which best identify the Resource. Copy and paste the resulting URL, together with the number of citations (example: https://europepmc.org/search?query=resourceAAB%20%2B%20organism : 35 citations). If necessary, indicate more than one URL, but do not exceed 3. If any extra explanation is needed, you can also add it to the text field. Moreover, if other citation counting tools are more representative of the usage of the Resource, please feel free to report the additional statistics.																												
e	<i>Dependency of other resources</i>	Indicate which resources depend on the Resource <i>Examples:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The UniLectin platform depends on SWISS-MODEL to display molecular interactions between small molecules and protein structures.</i> • <i>PeptideAtlas uses information about single amino acid variants and post-translational modifications in neXtProt to enable processing and display of data.</i> 																												
III Quality of Service																														
a	<i>Unique ID</i>	Indicate if the Resource provides persistent and unique identifiers and if yes, describe it.																												
b	<i>Data entries/records (data resources)</i>	<p><u>Cumulative</u> total number of entries or records to indicate the growth of the resource. Please provide a description and explanation on what an “entry” is.</p> <p><i>Example:</i></p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Entry</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Value at 31/12/2017</th> <th>Value at 31/12/2018</th> <th>Value at 31/12/2019</th> <th>Value at 31/07/2020</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><i>Species</i></td> <td><i>Number of Species in the Resource</i></td> <td>100</td> <td>200</td> <td>300</td> <td>400</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Genes</i></td> <td><i>Number of genes annotated in the Resource</i></td> <td>1000</td> <td>2000</td> <td>3000</td> <td>4000</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Variants</i></td> <td><i>Number of sequence variations present in the Resource</i></td> <td>200</td> <td>250</td> <td>400</td> <td>410</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>					Entry	Description	Value at 31/12/2017	Value at 31/12/2018	Value at 31/12/2019	Value at 31/07/2020	<i>Species</i>	<i>Number of Species in the Resource</i>	100	200	300	400	<i>Genes</i>	<i>Number of genes annotated in the Resource</i>	1000	2000	3000	4000	<i>Variants</i>	<i>Number of sequence variations present in the Resource</i>	200	250	400	410
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d	<i>Use of community-recognized standards for (meta)data</i>	Which community-recognized standards are used for metadata and data (e.g. MIAME, JATS, INSDC features, ontologies)? Provide a link to documentation.																												
e	<i>Data availability & access (data resources)</i>	<p>Data sharing services: list services through which data is shared (e.g. website, APIs, FTP, TripleStore)</p> <p>Data sharing formats: list formats for available data (e.g. plain text, FASTA, XML, RDF, Dublin Core, tsv, JSON)</p>																												
f	<i>Customer service - Training</i>	<p><u>Helpdesk</u>: does the Resource run a helpdesk?</p> <p><u>User feedback</u>: how does the Resource seek and incorporate user input into service design decisions?</p>																												

		<u>User training</u> : which training is offered by the Resource? (face2face training, eLearning, etc.)																														
IV Legal and funding infrastructure																																
a	<i>Scientific advisory board</i>	Does the Resource have an external independent Advisory Committee with scientists and/or users (other than the SIB SAB)?																														
b	<i>Legal framework supporting Open Science?</i>	Does the Resource have terms of use or a licence that enables the reuse and remixing of data? (see Open Definition for a list of open licenses) If yes, please include a link to terms of use or state licence designation (e.g. CC0, CC-BY, CC-BY-SA). Is the access to, and/or usage of, the Resource restricted in any way to the user or certain categories of users? If yes, please explain why. If the current legal framework does not support Open Science, do you plan to adopt an open licence?																														
c	<i>Licensing code: is it published on open access?</i>	Is the source code of the Resource published in open access (e.g. in GitHub)? If yes, please indicate under which licence and the relevant URLs.																														
d	<i>Sustainable support and funding</i>	Describe what has been and what will be undertaken to seek additional funds from other sources.																														
e	<i>Staff effort (how many FTEs?) and funding</i>	<p>Overview of all the available funding for the Resource during the period 2017–2021, as well as FTEs devoted to the Resource, including the PI working time. Please separate figures for infrastructure/service from figures for research. If the same grant funds both infrastructure and research, fill in two separate lines (see example below). Please specify the type of funding in the first column e.g. SNFS, university, European Commission, or any other source.</p> <p>Some of the rows are prefilled with information from 2019's report, please complete with the new data and when data is missing:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Type of funding</th> <th>Infrastructure / Research</th> <th>Period of funding</th> <th>Amount (CHF)</th> <th>FTEs</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>SIB</td> <td><i>Infrastructure</i></td> <td><i>Jan 2018 - Dec 2019</i></td> <td><i>XXX</i></td> <td><i>YYY</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td>UniBas</td> <td><i>Infrastructure</i></td> <td><i>Jan 2018 - Dec 2018</i></td> <td><i>ZZZ</i></td> <td><i>JJJ</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td>UniBas</td> <td><i>Research</i></td> <td><i>Jan 2018 - Dec 2018</i></td> <td><i>QQQ</i></td> <td><i>VVV</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td>SNFS</td> <td><i>Research</i></td> <td><i>Jan 2019 - Dec 2019</i></td> <td><i>HHH</i></td> <td><i>III</i></td> </tr> <tr> <td>...</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Type of funding	Infrastructure / Research	Period of funding	Amount (CHF)	FTEs	SIB	<i>Infrastructure</i>	<i>Jan 2018 - Dec 2019</i>	<i>XXX</i>	<i>YYY</i>	UniBas	<i>Infrastructure</i>	<i>Jan 2018 - Dec 2018</i>	<i>ZZZ</i>	<i>JJJ</i>	UniBas	<i>Research</i>	<i>Jan 2018 - Dec 2018</i>	<i>QQQ</i>	<i>VVV</i>	SNFS	<i>Research</i>	<i>Jan 2019 - Dec 2019</i>	<i>HHH</i>	<i>III</i>	...				
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f	<i>SIB funding</i>	How was SIB funding used for the period January 2019 – December 2020? Please detail (in person-months) for what kind of work SIB funding has been used (for example: XX person-																														

		months for biocuration, YY person-months for code development, ZZ person-months for dataset selection).
V	<i>Impact and translational stories</i>	
a	<i>Counterfactual</i>	Description of how science would be affected if the Resource had not existed or was to disappear and not be replaced.
b	<i>Accelerating science</i>	Description of how much the Resource accelerates science: present one or more selected examples of how the resource has been used by its user community, showcasing the importance of the Resource for advancing science. These “translational stories” help SIB to show its impact to audiences such as policy makers and funders and help the SAB to assess the Resource.
c	<i>Visibility</i>	What actions has the Resource taken to increase visibility within its potential user community?

VI	<i>SIB</i>	
a	<i>Benefits</i>	How does your Resource contribute to SIB in terms of scientific credibility, visibility or any other aspect?
b	<i>Participation</i>	Describe your contributions to SIB in the last 2 years, and how you see your involvement in the coming years